

Supplementary Materials

Supplementary Table 1 Rubber Hand Illusion questionnaire.

Question number	Question
1.	It seemed as though the touch I felt was caused by the paintbrush I could see touching the rubber hand.
2.	It felt as if the rubber hand was my hand.
3.	It felt as if my (real) hand was turning 'rubbery'.
4.	I found the touch of the paintbrush on my hand was pleasant.
5.	It seemed as if I might have more than one right* hand or arm.
6.	I found myself liking the rubber hand.
7.	It seemed as if I was feeling the touch of the paintbrush in the location where I saw the rubber hand being touched.
8.	It felt as if my (real) hand was getting cold.
9.	I felt the room temperature change during the experiment.
10.	The rubber hand began to resemble my own (real) hand, in terms of shape, skin tone, freckles or some other visual feature.
11.	It seemed as if I was in two different locations at the same time

The critical 'illusion' items are in **BOLD**. The remaining eight statements were 'mock' items.

Questions 1 and 7 scores were averaged to create a "hand stroking illusion" score.

Question 2 score was used to create a "hand ownership illusion" score.

Supplementary Table 2 Individual patient DBS setting Amplitude, Pulse Width and Frequency settings.

	Right DBS Amplitude	Right DBS Pulse Width	Right DBS Freq	Left DBS Amplitude	Left DBS Pulse Width	Left DBS Freq
Patient 1	2.2	60	130	1	60	130
Patient 2	3.1	60	120	3.7	110	120
Patient 3	3.7	90	160	3.4	60	160
Patient 4	2.5, 1.5	60	130	2.5, 1.5	60	130
Patient 5	2.6	60	110	2.4	60	110
Patient 6	2.4	60	130	2.4	60	130
Patient 7	3.2	60	170	2.6	90	170
Patient 8	4.6	60	130	4.6	60	130
Patient 9	0.65	60	130	3.15	60	130
Patient 10	3	60	130	3.2	60	130
Patient 11	3.6	90	130	3.4	90	130
Patient 12	3.5	60	130	3.6	60	130
Patient 13	4	60	130	1.6	60	130
Patient 14	2.55	60	130	2.55	60	130

Patient 15	2.35,2.5	60	125	2.35, 2.5	60	125
Patient 16	3.1	90	130	3.1	60	130
Patient 17	2.4	60	130	2.8	60	130
Patient 18	1.0, 2.0	60	115	2.5, 3.0	60	115
Patient 19	3.2	60	130	2.8	60	130
Patient 20	3.1	60	160	3.65	60	160
Patient 21	2.8	60	130	3.3	60	130

Supplementary Table 3 Sweetspot Explorer Settings

Setting	Chosen Parameter
E-field threshold [V/mm]	0.2
Voxels should be reached by at least X% of VTAs/E-Fields	20
Covariates	Gender, Age, MOCA (Side of disease onset only for UPDRS)
Normalize & Zero-Center VOI	z-score
Inspire Analysis by...	Custom
Statistical Test	T-Test
Against	Zero
Improvement Threshold	n.a.
Correction	Amplitude
Mirror Data	Yes (UPDRS), No (Drift, Illusion)
Consider Significant Voxels only	Yes $p < 0.05$
Show Negative Voxels	Yes
Show positive Voxels	Yes
Crossvalidation & Prediction	Leave-Nothing-Out, 300 Permutations
Base Prediction on	Mean of Scores
Post-hoc correct for group	No
E-field threshold [V/mm]	0.2

Supplementary Table 4 Network Mapping Explorer Settings

Setting	Chosen Parameter
Connectome	PPMI (Ewert 2017)
Resolution	2mm
Model Setup	Correlations (Horn 2017), Spearman
Covariates	Gender, Age, MOCA (Side of disease onset only for UPDRS)
Mirror Data	Yes (UPDRS), No (Drift, Illusion)
Consider Significant Voxels only	No
Show Negative Voxels	Yes
Show positive Voxels	Yes
Crossvalidation & Prediction	Leave-Nothing-Out, 300 Permutations

Base Similarity on	Spatial Correlations (Spearman)
Mask	Cortex
Post-hoc correct for group	No
Connectome	PPMI (Ewert 2017)
Resolution	2mm
Model Setup	Correlations (Horn 2017), Spearman
Covariates	Gender, Age, MOCA (Side of disease onset only for UPDRS)
Mirror Data	Yes (UPDRS), No (Drift, Illusion)

Supplementary Table 5 Mean R Value across Functional Segregations of Structural Regions of Interest

Functional / Structural ROI	UPDRS Improvement			Hand Stroking Illusion Improvement			Proprioceptive Drift Improvement				
	Mean R.	T stat.	P val.	Mean R.	T stat.	P val.	Mean R.	T stat.	P val.		
LH, Somatomotor A, ACC**	-0.06	10.70	1.E-13	LH, Somatomotor A, ACC**	0.52	11.01	6.E-14	LH, Saliency B, Pars Triangularis**	0.28	11.96	4.E-15
RH, Saliency A, ACC**	-0.06	10.53	2.E-13	LH, Saliency B, preSMA**	0.48	9.70	3.E-12	LH, Control B, OFC**	0.23	9.59	4.E-12
LH, Saliency A, preSMA**	-0.06	10.19	6.E-13	LH, Saliency A, preSMA**	0.46	8.91	3.E-11	LH, Control A, Pars Triangularis**	0.22	9.17	1.E-11
LH, Dorsal Attention B, preSMA**	-0.07	9.65	3.E-12	LH, Saliency B, ACC**	0.46	8.78	5.E-11	LH, Saliency B, OFC**	0.19	7.73	1.E-09
LH, Saliency B, ACC**	-0.07	9.35	8.E-12	LH, Control B, Pars Orbitalis**	0.46	8.70	6.E-11	LH, Control A, Pars Opercularis**	0.18	7.29	6.E-09
LH, Saliency A, ACC**	-0.07	9.15	1.E-11	LH, Limbic, OFC**	0.43	7.49	3.E-09	LH, Control B, DLPFC**	0.16	6.50	7.E-08
RH, Control A, ACC**	-0.08	8.83	4.E-11	LH, Control B, DLPFC**	0.42	7.26	6.E-09	RH, Limbic, OFC**	0.16	6.45	9.E-08

RH, Saliency B, preSMA**	-0.09	7.94	7.E-10	LH, Control B, OFC**	0.42	6.94	2.E-08	RH, Saliency A, Pars Triangularis**	0.16	6.42	1.E-07
RH, Saliency A, preSMA**	-0.09	7.91	8.E-10	LH, Dorsal Attention B, preSMA**	0.39	5.94	5.E-07	LH, Control B, vmPFC**	0.14	5.80	8.E-07
RH, Dorsal Attention B, Pars Opercularis**	-0.10	7.14	9.E-09	LH, Saliency B, DLPFC**	0.39	5.79	8.E-07	RH, Control B, Pars Orbitalis**	0.14	5.64	1.E-06
LH, Somatomotor A, SMA**	-0.11	5.83	7.E-07	LH, Saliency A, ACC**	0.37	5.05	9.E-06	LH, Saliency B, DLPFC**	0.14	5.41	3.E-06
RH, Control A, DLPFC**	-0.12	5.05	9.E-06	LH, Saliency A, Pars Triangularis**	0.37	4.91	1.E-05	RH, Control B, DLPFC**	0.12	4.83	2.E-05
RH, Saliency A, Pars Opercularis**	-0.12	4.63	3.E-05	LH, Control A, Pars Triangularis**	0.35	4.50	5.E-05	LH, Control B, Pars Orbitalis**	0.12	4.82	2.E-05
RH, Somatomotor A, ACC**	-0.14	3.56	9.E-04	LH, Somatomotor A, SMA**	0.34	3.93	3.E-04	RH, Saliency B, Pars Triangularis**	0.12	4.61	4.E-05
LH, Saliency B, preSMA	-0.14	2.97	0.005	LH, Saliency B, OFC**	0.34	3.91	3.E-04	LH, Limbic, OFC**	0.10	3.65	7.E-04
RH, Control A, Pars Opercularis	-0.14	2.95	0.005	RH, Saliency B, Pars Opercularis	0.31	2.82	0.007	RH, Control A, Pars Triangularis**	0.10	3.60	8.E-04
LH, Control A, Pars Opercularis	-0.15	2.43	0.020	LH, Control B, preSMA	0.30	2.46	0.018	LH, Control B, preSMA**	0.10	3.56	1.E-03
LH, Saliency B, Pars Opercularis	-0.15	2.32	0.025	LH, Somatomotor A, M1S1	0.30	2.23	0.031	RH, Saliency B, ACC	0.09	3.23	0.002
RH, Somatomotor A, SMA	-0.17	0.43	0.666	LH, Saliency B, Pars Opercularis	0.30	2.22	0.032	RH, Saliency B, DLPFC	0.07	2.37	0.022

RH, Saliency B, ACC	-0.18	-0.54	0.589	LH, Saliency B, Pars Triangularis	0.29	1.87	0.068	RH, Saliency B, Pars Opercularis	0.07	2.30	0.027
LH, Saliency A, Pars Triangularis	-0.18	-0.65	0.517	RH, Saliency B, preSMA	0.29	1.71	0.095	LH, Saliency A, Pars Triangularis	0.07	2.26	0.029
RH, Saliency B, Pars Opercularis	-0.19	-1.81	0.078	RH, Control A, Pars Opercularis	0.27	1.06	0.295	RH, Control B, vmPFC	0.04	1.23	0.225
LH, Control B, DLPFC	-0.20	-1.89	0.065	RH, Dorsal Attention B, Pars Opercularis	0.25	0.34	0.736	LH, Saliency B, Pars Opercularis	0.04	0.99	0.326
RH, Control B, vmPFC	-0.20	-1.99	0.054	LH, Control A, Pars Opercularis	0.24	-0.06	0.952	LH, Saliency A, Pars Opercularis	0.00	-0.72	0.476
RH, Saliency B, DLPFC	-0.20	-2.59	0.013	RH, Somatomotor A, ACC	0.24	-0.22	0.825	RH, Somatomotor A, M1S1	-0.01	-1.27	0.210
LH, Saliency B, DLPFC	-0.20	-2.62	0.012	RH, Saliency A, Pars Opercularis	0.22	-0.83	0.410	RH, Control A, ACC	-0.02	-1.69	0.099
LH, Saliency A, Pars Opercularis	-0.21	-3.01	0.004	RH, Saliency A, preSMA	0.22	-1.09	0.282	RH, Control A, DLPFC	-0.02	-1.92	0.062
LH, Limbic, OFC	-0.21	-3.07	0.004	LH, Control B, vmPFC	0.17	-2.85	0.007	RH, Saliency A, Pars Opercularis	-0.03	-2.06	0.046
RH, Somatomotor A, M1S1**	-0.21	-3.58	9.E-04	RH, Somatomotor A, SMA	0.17	-3.02	0.004	RH, Saliency A, ACC	-0.03	-2.19	0.034
LH, Control B, vmPFC**	-0.22	-3.94	2.E-04	LH, Saliency A, Pars Opercularis	0.17	-3.11	0.003	LH, Saliency B, preSMA**	-0.06	-3.53	0.001

LH, Control A, Pars Triangulari s**	-0.22	-4.44	6.E-05	RH, Control A, DLPFC**	0.13	-4.52	5.E-05	LH, Saliency B, ACC**	-0.07	-4.21	1.E-04
LH, Somatomo tor A, M1S1**	-0.23	-4.90	1.E-05	RH, Control B, vmPFC**	0.12	-4.91	1.E-05	RH, Dorsal Attention B, Pars Operculari s**	-0.08	-4.66	3.E-05
LH, Control B, Pars Orbitalis**	-0.24	-5.72	1.E-06	RH, Control A, ACC**	0.11	-5.15	7.E-06	RH, Control A, Pars Operculari s**	-0.09	-4.75	2.E-05
LH, Control B, preSMA**	-0.24	-5.77	9.E-07	RH, Saliency B, ACC**	0.11	-5.36	3.E-06	RH, Somatomo tor A, SMA**	-0.10	-5.41	3.E-06
LH, Control B, OFC**	-0.24	-5.81	7.E-07	RH, Saliency A, Pars Triangulari s**	0.08	-6.69	4.E-08	RH, Saliency A, preSMA**	-0.13	-6.72	4.E-08
RH, Control B, DLPFC**	-0.25	-6.53	7.E-08	RH, Somatomo tor A, M1S1**	0.07	-7.05	1.E-08	RH, Saliency B, preSMA*	-0.13	-6.80	3.E-08
RH, Control A, Pars Triangulari s**	-0.25	-6.65	5.E-08	RH, Saliency A, ACC**	0.06	-7.28	6.E-09	RH, Somatomo tor A, ACC**	-0.14	-7.15	9.E-09
RH, Saliency B, Pars Triangulari s**	-0.26	-7.56	2.E-09	RH, Control A, Pars Triangulari s**	0.02	-9.09	2.E-11	LH, Somatomo tor A, M1S1**	-0.15	-7.64	2.E-09
RH, Control B, Pars Orbitalis**	-0.27	-8.43	1.E-10	RH, Saliency B, DLPFC**	-0.01	-10.10	8.E-13	LH, Saliency A, ACC**	-0.20	-10.10	8.E-13
LH, Saliency B, OFC**	-0.27	-8.89	3.E-11	RH, Control B, DLPFC**	-0.01	-10.36	4.E-13	LH, Somatomo tor A, SMA**	-0.23	-11.18	4.E-14
LH, Saliency B, Pars Triangulari s**	-0.28	-9.28	1.E-11	RH, Saliency B, Pars Triangulari s**	-0.02	-10.43	3.E-13	LH, Saliency A, preSMA**	-0.23	-11.50	1.E-14
RH, Limbic, OFC**	-0.29	-10.93	7.E-14	RH, Control B, Pars Orbitalis**	-0.06	-12.10	3.E-15	LH, Dorsal Attention B, preSMA**	-0.25	-12.12	3.E-15

RH, Salience A, Pars Triangulari s**	-0.29	-10.96	7.E-14	RH, Limbic, OFC**	-0.09	-13.31	2.E-16	LH, Somatomo tor A, ACC**	-0.28	-13.77	9.E-16
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LH: Left hemisphere, RH: Right hemisphere, UPDRS: Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale part III, vmPFC: Ventromedial prefrontal cortex, DLPPFC: Dorsolateral prefrontal cortex, OFC: Orbitofrontal cortex, ACC: Anterior cingulate cortex, preSMA: Pre-Supplementary motor area, SMA: Supplementary motor area, M1S1: Primary motor and primary sensory cortex.
Distribution is normal as per Lilliefors test for normality.

** Significant after Bonferroni correction to $p < 0.0012$

PPMI85 Fibers passing through all VTAs

A

DKT cortical parcellation atlas overlying Fiber coverage

B

Supplementary Figure 1. A. Cortical Parcellation Atlas Overlap with all Stimulated Fibers from Structural Connectome. Three dimensional visualization, left hemisphere sagittal view, of all fibers on the PPMI85 (Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative; www.ppmi-info.org) structural diffusion tractography (DTI) normative connectome that pass through all VTAs of all patients, **B.** The Klein cortical parcellation atlas (DKT labeling protocol) demonstrating in 3D cortical parcels that overlie the fibers from (A). Bright Red = postcentral, bright purple = precentral, brown = caudal middle frontal, aqua = superior frontal, indigo = rostral middle frontal, bright purple = frontal pole, pink = medial orbital frontal, dark green = pars orbitalis, orange = pars triangularis, beige = pars opercularis.

Supplementary Figure 2. A-E. Bell Curves Produced by Cross-Validation. Performed for external validity with a leave-nothing-out 300 permutation bootstrapping analysis, also showing unpermuted result p value, **A.** Sweetspot explorer result for unified Parkinson's disease rating score III (UPDRS) improvement (sweetspots and sourspots), **B.** Sweetspot explorer result for right hand proprioceptive drift improvement (sweetspots only), **C.** Network mapping explorer result for UPDRS improvement, **D.** Network mapping explorer result for right hand proprioceptive drift improvement, **E.** Network mapping explorer result for right hand stroking illusion score improvement.

Supplementary Methods: The Rubber Hand Illusion Testing Protocol.

The RHI experiment has been described by Ding et al. (2017). Participants sat facing a black box with three compartments and darkened glass top, with the investigator opposite. The participant's hand was positioned in a lateral compartment matching the posture of a rubber hand 20 cm away in a central compartment. Participants made verbal baseline estimates of their middle finger position. The center compartment was illuminated to reveal the rubber hand. Two identical brushes stroked the participant's hidden hand and the visible rubber hand. In synchronous conditions, the same finger was stroked simultaneously (spatial and temporal congruence). In asynchronous conditions, different fingers were stroked in temporally discordant fashion (spatial and temporal incongruence). After two minutes, participants made post-stroking position estimates. The difference between baseline and final estimates defined proprioceptive drift. Trials concluded with questionnaire completion (Supplementary Table 1). Testing sessions comprised two synchronous and two asynchronous trials in randomized order. All participants completed at least two testing sessions, with randomized on/off order. On/off stimulation was defined as STN stimulation having been switched on/off for at least 30 minutes. Patients took usual dopaminergic medication in both states. A neurologist (CD), unblinded to DBS settings, assessed motor severity using

MDS-UPDRS Part III with patients on and off stimulation. MoCA was performed on stimulation with usual PD medication.

Ding C, Palmer CJ, Hohwy J, Youssef GJ, Paton B, Tsuchiya N, Stout JC, Thyagarajan D. Parkinson's disease alters multisensory perception: Insights from the Rubber Hand Illusion. Neuropsychologia. 2017 Mar;97:38-45. doi: 10.1016/j.neuropsychologia.2017.01.031. Epub 2017 Jan 31. PMID: 28153639.